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SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS OF COGNITIVE RADIO SYSTEM USING MATLAB

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand of wireless applications has put a lot of limitations on the use of available radio spectrum is limited and precious resource. Many survey of spectrum utilization shows that entire spectrum is not used at all the times, so many of the radio spectrum is underutilized. Some of the frequency bands in the spectrum are unoccupied, some of the frequency bands less occupied and few bands are over utilized. Cognitive radio system is a technique which overcomes that spectrum underutilization. Cognitive radio is a technique where secondary user looks for a free band to use when primary user is not in use of its licensed band. A function of cognitive radio is called Spectrum sensing which enables to search for the free bands and it helps to detect the spectrum hole (frequency band which is free enough to be used) which can be utilized by secondary user with high spectral resolution capability. The idea of simulation and analysis of Cognitive Radio System to reuse unused spectrum to increase the total system capacity was brought in this paper and this work digs into the practical implementation of a Cognitive radio system. MATLAB R2007b (version7.5) has been used to test the performance of Cognitive radio dynamically

KEYWORDS

Cognitive Radio, Spectrum Sensing, Energy detection and Periodogram, MATLAB

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SPECTRUM SENSING TECHNIQUES IN COGNITIVE RADIO NETWORKS: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand of wireless applications has put a lot of constraints on the usage of available radio spectrum which is limited and precious resource. However, a fixed spectrum assignment has lead to under utilisation of spectrum as a great portion of licensed spectrum is not effectively utilised. Cognitive radio is a promising technology which provides a novel way to improve utilisation efficiency of available electromagnetic spectrum. Spectrum sensing helps to detect the spectrum holes (underutilised bands of the spectrum) providing high spectral resolution capability. In this paper, survey of spectrum sensing techniques is presented. The challenges and issues involved in implementation of spectrum sensing techniques are discussed in detail giving comparative study of various methodologies.

KEYWORDS

Cognitive Radio, Dynamic Spectrum Access, Spectrum Sensing, Signal Processing Techniques

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SURVEY ON SCHEDULING AND RADIO RESOURCES ALLOCATION IN LTE

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on an essential task of the enhanced NodeB eNodeB element in LTE architecture, the Radio Resource Manager RRM, which aims to accept or reject requests for connection to the network based on some constraints and ensuring optimal distribution of radio resources between Users Equipments UEs. Its main functionalities include Admission Control AC and Packet Scheduling PS. This paper will center mainly on the PS part of the RRM task, which performs the radio resource allocation in both uplink and downlink directions. Several approaches and algorithms have been proposed in the literature to address this need (allocate resources efficiently), the diversity and multitude of algorithms is related to the factors considered for the optimal management of radio resource, specifically, the traffic type and the QoS (Quality of Service) requested by the UE. In this article, an art's state of the radio resource allocation strategies and a detailed study of several scheduling algorithms proposed for LTE (uplink and downlink) are made. Therefore, we offer our evaluation and criticism.

KEYWORDS

Enhanced NodeB eNodeB, LTE, Radio Resource manager RRM, Admission Control AC, Packet Scheduler PS.

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OPTIMIZED PERFORMANCE WITH SAP NET WEAVER BI ACCELERATOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the SAP Net weaver BI accelerator and its features and how the accelerator can be used for optimized performance in any IT industry. The objective is to provide the best practices and solutions for current challenges in using SAP Net weaver BI Accelerator in any large scale business industries across the world.

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PERFORMANCE MONITORING AND RESOURCE PROVISIONING IN NGN OVER ETOM

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ABSTRACT

This paper is about the implementation of performance monitoring and resource availability solution in transport stratum of Next Generation Network (NGN) over Enhanced Telecom Operations Map (eTOM) framework. Continuous monitoring of performance is done to ensure consistent Quality of Service (QoS) to the users. Monitoring of network parameters such as delay, delay variation, path unavailability, packet loss ratio is done in the transport stratum of next generation network architecture. Resource and Admission Control Functions (RACF) will interact with Management functions for performance measurement of NGN transport control traffic and transport services and allocate resources to the customers whose QoS requirements are satisfied. The above functionalities are mapped into NGN business elements, defined by eTOM framework.

KEYWORDS

Next Generation Networks, Resource availability, Quality of Service, Performance Monitoring, eTOM

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THE IMPACT OF CELL SITE RE-HOMING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF UMTS CORE NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile operators currently prefer optimizing their radio networks via re-homing or cutting over the cell sites in 2G or 3G networks. The core network, as the parental part of radio network, is inevitably impacted by the re-homing in radio domain. This paper introduces the cell site re-homing in radio network and analyzes its impact on the performance of GSM/UMTS core network. The possible re-homing models are created and analyzed for core networks. The paper concludes that appropriate re-homing in radio domain, using correct algorithms, not only optimizes the radio network but also helps improve the QoS of the core network and saves the carriers' OPEX and CAPEX on their core networks.

KEYWORDS

UMTS, WCDMA, GSM, Core Network, Rehomeing, Network Optimization, Network Dimension, Network Plan

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VALIDATION STUDY OF PATH LOSS MODELS ON WIMAX AT 2.6 GHZ FREQUENCY BAND IN SUBURBAN ENVIRONMENT FOR CELL SIZE PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

The radio wave propagation in form of path loss model plays very significant role in planning of any wireless communication network. Measurement of signal strength of OFDM driven WiMAX technology at 2.6 GHz band is taken in Suburban Town of India. The results are analyzed and compared with Empirical path loss models such as Hata-Okumura, Modified Hata and COST-231Hata. COST-231 model shows highest path loss for suburban environment. These analyzed results establish that COST-231 model is suitable for suburban environment also. Threshold RSSI estimates cell coverage probability in the area.

KEYWORDS

OFDM, WiMAX, IEEE 802.16, path loss exponent, Rayleigh fading, RSSI, CINR

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IMAGE COMPRESSION AND WATERMARKING SCHEME USING SCALAR QUANTIZATION

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents a new compression technique and image watermarking algorithm based on Contourlet Transform (CT). For image compression, an energy based quantization is used. Scalar quantization is explored for image watermarking. Double filter bank structure is used in CT. The Laplacian Pyramid (LP) is used to capture the point discontinuities, and then followed by a Directional Filter Bank (DFB) to link point discontinuities. The coefficients of down sampled low pass version of LP decomposed image are re-ordered in a pre-determined manner and prediction algorithm is used to reduce entropy (bits/pixel). In addition, the coefficients of CT are quantized based on the energy in the particular band. The superiority of proposed algorithm to JPEG is observed in terms of reduced blocking artifacts. The results are also compared with wavelet transform (WT). Superiority of CT to WT is observed when the image contains more contours. The watermark image is embedded in the low pass image of contourlet decomposition. The watermark can be extracted with minimum error. In terms of PSNR, the visual quality of the watermarked image is exceptional. The proposed algorithm is robust to many image attacks and suitable for copyright protection applications.

KEYWORDS-

Contourlet Transform, Directional Filter Bank, Laplacian Pyramid, Topological re-ordering, Quantization.

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HIGH PERFORMANCE ETHERNET PACKET PROCESSOR CORE FOR NEXT GENERATION NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

As the demand for high speed Internet significantly increasing to meet the requirement of large data transfers, real-time communication and High Definition (HD) multimedia transfer over IP, the IP based network products architecture must evolve and change. Application specific processors require high performance, low power and high degree of programmability is the limitation in many general processor based applications. This paper describes the design of Ethernet packet processor for system-on-chip (SoC) which performs all core packet processing functions, including segmentation and reassembly, packetization classification, route and queue management which will speedup switching/routing performance making it more suitable for Next Generation Networks (NGN). Ethernet packet processor design can be configured for use with multiple projects targeted to a FPGA device the system is designed to support 1/10/20/40/100 Gigabit links with a speed and performance advantage. VHDL has been used to implement and simulated the required functions in FPGA.

KEYWORDS

Ethernet, SoC, FPGA, NGN, LAN Router and Switches, IP networks, 1/10/20/40/100 Gigabit

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ADAPTIVE ROUTING ALGORITHM FOR MANET: TERMITE

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Ad hoc network consists of a set of mobile nodes. This network does not have any infrastructure or central administration, hence it is called infrastructure less network. As the nodes are mobile, it is very difficult to find the path between two end points. This paper presents a solution for finding path between nodes in mobile ad hoc network. Termite is an innovative algorithm for packet routing in communication networks. Termite is an adaptive, distributed, mobile-agents-based algorithm which was inspired by recent work on the ant colony metaphor. According to this algorithm, a group of mobile agents (or artificial termites) build paths between pair of nodes; exploring the network concurrently and exchanging obtained information to update the routing tables. Some of the parameters used to evaluate its performance are packet delays and throughput. The results of this algorithm shows better throughput as compared to existing algorithms. So, Termite algorithm is a promising alternative for routing of data in commercial networks.

KEYWORDS

Routing algorithm, Swarm intelligence, Mobile agents, Pheromone.

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